

**Effects of magnetic field on natural convective heat transfer of nanofluid flow
in a two-dimensional rectangular cavity in the presence of constant-
temperature triangular blades on the bottom wall**

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Abstract

The simulation of the natural convective heat transfer (HTR) of nanofluid (NFD) flow in a two-dimensional rectangular cavity is performed in this paper. A magnetic field (MFD) is placed close to the cavity and the NFD. The top wall of the cavity is cold, and the side walls are insulated. Three isothermal triangular blades are mounted on the bottom wall at the same temperature as the wall. By changing the height of one of these blades from 0.1 to 0.7 and changing the location of this blade, three HTR models are estimated. Lattice Boltzmann method (LBM) and an in-house code are used for the simulations. The findings show that including the MFD lowers the Nu. The Nu is reduced with the Ha. Enhancing the length of the blades

intensifies the average Nu for three studied models so that an increment in the blade length from 0.1 to 0.7 enhances the Nu from 9.3% to 18.5%, respectively. For the blade length of 0.1 and 0.3, model 2 has the maximum Nu, while model 1 has the maximum Nu for the blade length of 0.5 and 0.7.

Keywords: Nanofluid, Blade, Free convective heat transfer, Magnetic field, Cavity

1- Introduction

An enhancement in the HTR rate by improving the thermal properties of the working fluid in heating systems has received serious attention from researchers [1, 2]. Increasing the thermal conductivity of liquids was done in the past years by adding metal microparticles [3]. However, the rapid sedimentation of these particles caused blockage of channels, erosion of walls, and high pressure drop, limiting the use of this technology in experimental investigations. For the first time, Choi [4] utilized the term NFD for a fluid with suspending metal nanoparticles. Adding nanoparticles to the fluid creates a NFD with a higher thermal conductivity than the base fluid [5]. In addition, the problems of rapid sedimentation and channel blockage have also been solved [6]. One of the applications of NFDs in cavities is supposed to enhance HTR [7-9]. Hosseini Abadshapoori [10] examined the effect of using copper/water NFD as a coolant in a hot tube inside a square cavity using LBM. When the Richardson number varied, it was thought that the volume percentage of nanoparticles remained constant. The results demonstrated the greater efficacy of nanoparticles for natural convection HTR. Nevertheless, they discovered that the efficiency of nanoparticles might be drastically diminished by the deposition of nanoparticles at high Richardson numbers. Forced convective flow and setups with vast distances are comparable to natural convective flow. Issakhov et al. [11] provided the numerical HTR findings of a two-dimensional laminar flow in the channel with various inclination degrees and forward and

backward steps, considering buoyancy force for various bottom wall lengths. The effect of inclination angle was assessed on the velocity and temperature distribution. According to reports, the flow fluctuation and temperature distribution in the channel are significantly influenced by the length of the lowest half of the channel. It should be noted that the flow and temperature distribution were also significantly impacted by the tilt angle. The primary swirl region's form changes due to the buoyancy force, but the number of vortices remains constant, and their sizes vary for all inclination degrees. It should also be observed that the center of the channel cools more effectively when the buoyancy force is considered. The impact of a non-uniform MFD on mixed convective HTR of water/iron oxide NFD flow in an open cavity was evaluated by Shaker et al. [12]. The MFD was built using wires that could transport current. On the flow pattern, volume fraction distribution of nanoparticles, and average Nu, the impact of varying various factors including, magnetic number, Reynolds number, and horizontal distance of wires from the hollow wall were assessed. The findings showed that the Kelvin force's impact on applying a non-uniform MFD causes a change in the flow pattern and the formation of new vortices in the fluid flow. The average Nu was decreased by using a weak MFD. An increase in the magnetic number led to a significant improvement in the average Nu. The average Nu increased by a high of 57.07%.

Natural convective in heat exchangers has very important applications, especially in some sensitive industries. Natural convection occurs in closed cavities with temperature differences inside the cavity, and thus, researchers have studied this type of HTR [13, 14]. One of the applications of NFDs is enhancing heat transfer in heat exchangers [15]. Various researchers have also utilized NFDs in cavities to improve HTR [16]. The MFD was also examined in the cavities by researchers. This research examines the free convection HTR of an NFD in a closed

cavity when an MFD is applied based on these scenarios. There are three triangular blades in the hollow. HTR is studied by adjusting the length of one of the blades. Also, three different models of blade arrangement are introduced by changing the location of this blade and the impact of magnetic strength is also assessed.

2- Problem definition and governing equations

2-1- Geometry

The geometry consists of a rectangular cavity filled with NFD under a horizontal MFD (Fig. 1). The top wall is cold, and the two side walls are insulated. Three isothermal triangular blades with the same temperature are mounted on the hot bottom wall. This study is done by changing the height of one of the blades from 0.1 to 0.7. Also, by changing the location of this blade, three arrangements of blades are evaluated.

Fig. 1. A schematic of the cavity and the different models.

2-2- Lattice Boltzmann method

In the LBM, the governing equation is the Boltzmann equation. By discretizing this equation for space and time, the density distribution function is obtained as Eq. 1 [17].

$$f_i(\vec{x} + \vec{C}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = f_i(\vec{x}, t) - \frac{\Delta t}{\tau_\vartheta} [(f_i(\vec{x}, t) - f_i^{eq}(\vec{x}, t))] \quad (1)$$

The most typical two-dimensional model used in this research is the D2Q9 one. There are eight permitted motion directions in this model, which are shown in Fig. 2. In this figure 2, \vec{C}_i is expressed as Eq. 2, where $C = \Delta x / \Delta t$ is the velocity of virtual particles on the grid [17].

$$\begin{cases} \vec{C}_i = 0 & i = 0 \\ \vec{C}_i = C (\cos \theta_i, \sin \theta_i) & \theta_i = 0.5\pi(i - 1) \quad i = 1,2,3,4 \\ \vec{C}_i = C\sqrt{2} (\cos \theta_i, \sin \theta_i) & \theta_i = 0.5\pi + 0.25\pi \quad i = 5,6,7,8 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The equilibrium distribution function is also defined as Eq. 3 [17].

$$f_i^{(eq)} = \omega_i \rho \left[1 + 3 \frac{\vec{C}_i \cdot \vec{u}}{c^2} + \frac{9}{2} \frac{(\vec{C}_i \cdot \vec{u})^2}{c^4} - \frac{3}{2} \frac{u^2}{c^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

where ρ and \vec{u} are macroscopic properties and ω_i are the weight coefficients of the equilibrium distribution function in the direction i and are expressed as Eq. 4:

$$\omega_i = \begin{cases} \frac{4}{9} & i = 0 \\ \frac{1}{9} & i = 1,2,3,4 \\ \frac{1}{36} & i = 5,6,7,8 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The relaxation time and kinematic viscosity are correlated to drive the Navier-Stokes equation from the Boltzmann equation [17]:

$$\vartheta = c_s^2 \Delta t (\tau_\vartheta - 0.5) \quad (5)$$

Here, c_s is the speed of sound, which is $c/\sqrt{3}$ on the Boltzmann lattice. If the value of kinematic viscosity is physically meaningful, $\tau_\vartheta > 0.5$. The details of obtaining this relation are given in Ref. [18].

Macroscopic properties such as fluid density and velocity are calculated as follows [17]:

$$\rho = \sum_{i=0}^8 f_i \quad (6)$$

$$\rho \vec{u} = \sum_{i=0}^8 \vec{C}_i f_i \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Discretized velocity vectors for the D2Q9 model.

The solution of the lattice Boltzmann equation is done in two stages: collision and diffusion. Eq. 8 shows the collision phase and Eq. 9 represents the diffusion phase:

$$\tilde{f}_i(\vec{x}, t + \Delta t) = f_i(\vec{x}, t) - \frac{\Delta t}{\tau_\theta} [(f_i(\vec{x}, t) - f_i^{eq}(\vec{x}, t))] \quad (8)$$

$$f_i(\vec{x} + \vec{C}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = \tilde{f}_i(\vec{x}, t + \Delta t) \quad (9)$$

where \tilde{f}_i indicates the distribution function after the collision. The external force in the free convective HTR problems is the buoyancy force that appears in the flow equation. To apply the external force, the equation of the lattice Boltzmann is converted into the following equation [36]:

$$f_i(\vec{x} + \vec{C}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = f_i(\vec{x}, t) - \frac{\Delta t}{\tau_g} [(f_i(\vec{x}, t) - f_i^{eq}(\vec{x}, t))] + \Delta t F_i(\vec{x}, t) \cdot \frac{\vec{C}_i}{C_s^2} \quad (10)$$

The Boussinesq approach, which takes into account the linear variations in density with temperature, is used to compute the buoyancy force. Hence [17]:

$$F_x = w_i \rho \left[\frac{Ha^2 \mu}{H^2} (v \sin(\gamma) \cos(\gamma) - (u \sin^2(\gamma))) \right] \quad (11)$$

Here, g_y is the gravitational acceleration in the y-direction and T_∞ is the minimum temperature ($T_\infty=0$). By neglecting the viscous losses, the energy equation of the lattice Boltzmann is defined as Eq. 12 [36]:

$$g_i(\vec{x} + \vec{C}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = g_i(\vec{x}, t) - \frac{\Delta t}{\tau_T} [(g_i(\vec{x}, t) - g_i^{eq}(\vec{x}, t))] \quad (12)$$

Here, the energy distribution function along the discretized velocity is indicated by g_i , and the equilibrium energy distribution function and macroscopic temperature are expressed as follows, respectively [17]:

$$g_i^{(eq)} = \omega_i T \left[1 + 3 \frac{\vec{c}_i \cdot \vec{u}}{c^2} + \frac{9}{2} \frac{(\vec{c}_i \cdot \vec{u})^2}{c^4} - \frac{3}{2} \frac{\vec{u}^2}{c^2} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$T = \sum_{i=0}^8 g_i \quad (14)$$

The thermal diffusion coefficient may be stated as Eq. 15 to get the energy equation from the lattice Boltzmann's thermal equation [59].

$$\alpha = C_s^2 \Delta t (\tau_T - 0.5) \quad (15)$$

To have a positive value for α , $\tau_T > 0.5$.

2-3- Application of boundary conditions

The dimensionless parameters of the problem are

$$X^* = \frac{x}{W} \quad . Y^* = \frac{y}{W} \quad . U = \frac{uW}{\alpha_f} \quad . V = \frac{vW}{\alpha_f} \quad (16)$$

$$\alpha^* = \frac{\alpha_{nf}}{\alpha_f} \quad \mu = \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\mu_f} \quad k = \frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} \quad \theta = \frac{T-T_C}{\Delta T}$$

$$Pr = \frac{\vartheta}{\alpha} \quad Ra = \frac{g_y \beta H^3 \Delta T}{\vartheta \alpha}$$

Using dimensionless equations, the boundary conditions are expressed as Eqs. 17 to 19.

Bottom wall and blades:

$$U = V = 0 \quad \theta = 1 \quad (17)$$

Top wall:

$$U = V = 0 \quad \theta = 0 \quad (18)$$

Side walls

$$U = V = 0 \quad \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (19)$$

The approach suggested by Joe et al. [38] is utilized to determine the velocity and temperature on the curved boundary. A schematic of the curved border and the grid used in this approach is shown in Fig. 3. The nodes in the solid boundary that are closest to the curved boundary are the only ones in this approach that are included in the calculation domain. These nodes are identified by the subscript b. The subscript w denotes where the grid's octagon lines and the curving border meet. Moreover, f and ff denote the first and second nodes in each line within the computational domain. This method uses the extrapolation approximation of the density distribution functions and energy distribution functions related to the points adjacent to the boundary within the solution domain and uses the temperature and velocity of the curved boundary to calculate the amounts of equilibrium distribution functions (density and energy) of the adjacent solid points close to the curved boundary after the collision stage. The estimated distribution functions are sent to the solution domain's nodes during the diffusion stage. Depending on where the grid directions and the curved boundary connect, the extrapolation approximation is either of the first

Fig. 3. Curved wall boundary and grid.

2-4- Governing equations for NFD

The Newtonian, incompressible, single-phase nature of the NFD is assumed. With the exception of the density in the buoyancy equation, whose changes are achieved by using the Boussinesq approximation, its physical attributes are also regarded as constant with respect to temperature variations. The assumption of identical velocity between solid nanoparticles and base fluid particles results from the use of a single-phase model. The steady, laminar, and radiation-free flow in two dimensions. Table 1 lists the thermophysical characteristics of base fluid and nanoparticles. Eq. 23 is the effective density of NFD, Eq. 24 is the heat capacity, and Eq. 25 is the definition of the effective thermal expansion of NFD based on Ref. [20].

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \varphi)\rho_f + \varphi\rho_p \quad (23)$$

$$(C_p)_{nf} = \left[\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\varphi\rho_p}{(1-\varphi)\rho_f}} \frac{(C_p)_p}{(C_p)_f} + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\varphi\rho_p}{(1-\varphi)\rho_f}} \right] (C_p)_{nf} \quad (24)$$

$$B_{nf} = \left[\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\varphi\rho_p}{(1-\varphi)\rho_f}} \frac{\beta_p}{\beta_f} + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\varphi\rho_p}{(1-\varphi)\rho_f}} \right] B_f \quad (25)$$

Brinkman model [21] is utilized for NFD viscosity, and Hamilton and Kreuzer model [22] is employed for NFD thermal conductivity:

$$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\varphi)^{2.5}} \quad (26)$$

$$k_{nf} = k_f \left(\frac{k_p + (n-1)k_f - (k_f - k_p)(n-1)\varphi}{k_p + (n-1)k_f + (k_f - k_p)\varphi} \right) \quad (27)$$

Table 1. Thermophysical properties of water and Al₂O₃ [23].

	k (W/m.K)	ρ (kg/m ³)	μ (kg/m.s)	C_p (J/kg.K)
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Water	0.613	997.1	0.001	4179
Al_2O_3	40	3970	-	765

3- Grid study and validation

In order to control the correctness of the in-house code, verification is done using experimental data since the accuracy of the experimental work is higher than numerical results. The experimental data of Crane and Jesse Mere [24] are used for the validation. The values of the horizontal velocity in the cavity obtained from the present work and the experimental ones are compared in Fig. 4, indicating that the present results are in good agreement with the experimental data.

Fig. 4. Dimensionless horizontal velocity in the middle line of the cavity: comparison between the present work and Ref. [24].

To achieve a suitable grid, various simulations are performed with different grid resolutions and the output values are compared. Fig. 5 depicts the average Nu for three models of the blade arrangement using different grid resolutions. Based on these results, it can be seen that the grid with 76800 nodes can be selected as the optimal grid.

Fig. 5. The effect of the number of grid points on the average Nu for three blade arrangement models and a blade length of 0.1.

4- Results and discussion

Fig. 6. Streamline contours for different blade arrangement models and four blade lengths.

Fig. 6 illustrates the streamline contours for different blade arrangement models and four blade lengths. The number of vortices and the direction of rotation of the vortices strongly depend on the length of the blades and the examined model. The enlargement of the third blade is very effective on the number of vortices. The existence of blades causes the parts inside the cavities to be divided into different parts. The rotation direction also depends on the blades. For some longer lengths of the blades, the rotation direction of the vortices is reversed. The bottom wall's blades' high temperature raises the NFD's temperature near these components. As a result, the NFD moves upwards from the sides of the walls and blades. The fluid moves upwards, especially from the side of the insulated wall and from the side of the blades. It goes down from the middle parts. The cooling of the NFD next to the top wall makes it heavier, and the fluid returns to the bottom wall. By raising the temperature of the NFD in the bottom section of the cavity, an increase in the blade length improves the buoyancy force. Yet, the velocity of the NFD in the cavity is decreased due to the reduction in cavity space.

Fig. 7. Temperature contours for different blade arrangement models and four blade lengths.

Fig. 7 depicts the temperature contours for different blade arrangement models and four blade lengths. It is observed that the bottom wall and the blades cause the NFD to enhance the temperature close to these parts. Also, the NFD is cooled on the side of the top wall. These temperature changes cause the buoyancy force to be created in the cavity and the NFD to move in the cavity. In most of the models, the NFD moves from the sharp tip of the blade towards the top wall and moves down from the sides of the insulated wall as well as the space between the two blades. For some models, such as the lengths of 1 and 0.1 of the blade, the NFD moves up from the side of the wall. This indicates that the changes in the length of the blades affect the location of the NFD motion towards up and down in the cavity. The enhancement in the length of the blades causes the parts of the hot NFD to be closer to the cold NFD, and as a result, the density of the isothermal lines in the parts of the cold wall that is under the blade becomes higher. By enhancing the length of the blades, the density of isothermal lines on the sharp parts

of the blades is increased, and the density of isothermal lines on the bottom wall is slightly reduced.

Fig. 8. Local Nu on the cold wall for the blade length of 0.1 and different blade arrangements.

Fig. 8 depicts the local Nu on the cold wall for the blade length of 0.1 and different blade arrangements. Comparing the local Nusselt diagram with the contours of temperature and velocity of NFD demonstrates that in the parts where the NFD moves up and collides with the top wall, the local Nu is maximal, and in the parts where the NFD collides with the bottom wall, the value of Nu is minimal. In this blade length, which is the shortest blade length, the space for moving the NFD in the cavity is larger, but the length of the hot wall is less than that for other blade lengths. For models 1 and 2, it can be seen that the diagram has three peaks, and the diagram has two peaks for model 3. The number of vortices formed is directly related to the number of peaks created in this diagram. It can be seen the amount of Nu is small on the sides of the insulated walls. In these parts, the Nu is lower because it is in the corner and the fluid is not well connected with it. Due to the strong convective HTR, the Nu is higher than 2. It reaches about 10 in some parts.

Fig. 9. Local Nu on the cold wall for the blade length of 0.3 and different blade arrangements.

Fig. 9 demonstrates the local Nu on the cold wall for the blade length of 0.3 and different blade arrangements. In the parts where the NFD leaves the cold wall and moves towards the hot wall, the amount of HTR is small because the temperature of the NFD is close to the temperature of the wall. The temperature reduction of the fluid caused the NFD to go down. For the blade length of 0.3, it can be seen that the diagram has two peaks for models 1 and 3 and the diagram has one peak for model 2. One of the peaks of models 1 and 3 is lower than the other two peaks. The shorter peak is located on, the smaller blade. Due to the smaller contact surface on the smaller blade, the NFD has a lower temperature. As a result, its temperature difference with the wall is smaller than the other two blades, leading to lower HTR on this blade. The motion of the hot fluid from the blades towards the top wall is due to the decrease in the density of the NFD on

these blades, which ultimately causes the colder fluid to be replaced and the hot fluid to go towards the top wall. The fluid then cools down and flows towards the bottom wall. Due to the strong convective of NFD in the cavity, the local Nu is extremely high in most parts, indicating high HTR in these parts.

Fig. 10. Local Nu on the cold surface for the blade length of 0.5 and different blade arrangements.

Fig. 10 demonstrates the local Nu on the cold surface for the blade length of 0.5 and different blade arrangements. The heated fluid on the blades and the bottom hot wall moves towards the top cold wall. When the hot NFD reaches the top wall, a high amount of HTR occurs in that part, which can be seen as a peak in the diagram. When the hot NFD reaches the top wall and collides with the top wall, the NFD moves along the cold wall to give heat to the cold wall and reduce the temperature. As the temperature of the NFD is reduced, the amount of HTR between the NFD

and the top wall is decreased. As the temperature of the NFD decreases, the fluid molecules become closer to each other, and the density of the fluid is enhanced. As a result, as the fluid gets colder, the fluid tends to move toward the bottom of the cavity. These parts, where the NFD leaves the cold wall can be seen as V-shaped in the diagram due to the proximity of the temperature of the NFD and the wall as well as the low HTR between them. When the cold NFD reaches the bottom wall, a high HTR occurs on this wall and the fluid starts to heat up again. By repeating this process, the vortices are formed inside the cavity.

Fig. 11. Local Nu on the cold surface for the blade length of 0.7 and different blade arrangements.

Fig. 11 illustrates the local Nu on the cold surface for the blade length of 0.7 and different blade arrangements. It can be seen that the number of the peaks and valleys formed on the diagrams is similar to each other for the blade length of 0.7. Quantitatively, the Nu for the three models are

similar. Three models are close to each other from the point of view of the formation of peaks and valleys. Due to the approximation of the blades, the Nu on the cold wall above these blades is also close to each other. For this length of the blade, three peaks are created in the local Nu. The hot fluid moves towards the cold wall, and the amount of HTR is significantly enhanced. In most of the parts, the local Nu is above two, and only in the beginning and end parts of the wall, the positional Nu is less than two. Due to the corner of these two parts, the flow penetration is low, and the HTR is weak, which causes the amount of HTR in these parts to be low. Thus, the Nu is less than 2. However, in most parts of the diagram, the local Nu is greater than 2 due to the high velocity of the fluid.

Table 2. Average Nu on the cold wall for the blade lengths from 0.1 to 0.7 and different blade arrangement models.

L	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
0.1	5.801	5.860	5.413
0.3	5.686	5.834	5.684
0.5	6.266	6.265	6.265
0.7	6.414	6.411	6.413

Table 2 illustrates the average Nu on the cold wall for the blade lengths from 0.1 to 0.7 and different blade arrangement models. Comparing different models reveals that changing the length of the blade is more effective than changing the arrangement of the blades. For the length of 0.1, model 2 has the maximum average Nu. For the length of 0.3, model 2 has the maximum HTR, but for the length of 0.5, model 1 has the maximum HTR. For the blade length of 0.7, model 1 has the maximum HTR. The effect of arrangement on the Nu is greater for lower heights of the blades because as the blade length becomes higher, the difference in the height of the

blades is reduced. Hence, the effect of changing the arrangement is decreased. The enhancement in the length of the blades causes the amount of average Nu to enhance. The enlargement of the hot surface in the cavity causes the amount of HTR to the cold wall to enhance due to the increment in the temperature of the NFD.

Table 3. Average Nu on the cold wall for different Ha and different blade arrangement models.

Ha	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
0	5.801	5.860	5.413
10	4.12	4.18	4.09
20	3.31	3.37	3.23
30	2.40	2.45	2.36

Table 3 shows the average Nu on the cold wall for different Ha and different blade arrangement models. An enhancement in the Ha affects the motion of the NFD in the cavity. As the Ha increases, the cavity's fluid velocity is reduced. It can be seen that the amount of Nu is decreased by reducing the velocity of the NFD for different models. The higher the Ha, the greater the MFD strength. Hence, the reduction in the average Nu is enhanced with the Ha. The Nu reduction is almost the same for different blade arrangement models. The highest Nu occurred in Ha 0 and in model 2.

4- Conclusions

In this study, a two-dimensional rectangular cavity is used to simulate the natural convective HTR of NFD flow. The lower hot wall is equipped with three triangular blades. Three models are introduced by modifying the length of a blade from 0.1 to 0.7 and moving the blade's placement. The findings of this investigation show:

1- An increment in the Ha causes the average Nu in the cavity to reduce for all models. The more Ha , the more Nu reduction.

2- The greatest quantity of HTR is seen in the areas of the cold wall where the hot fluid collides. The least quantity of Nu is found in the areas of the cold wall where the cold fluid exits the wall.

3- Enhancing the length of the blade causes the increment of the average Nu on the top wall.

4- For two blade lengths of 0.1 and 0.3, model 2 has the maximum average Nu .

5- For the blade lengths of 0.5 and 0.5, model 1 has the maximum HTR.

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